

Antimony and Mercury Compounds of Quinoline and *iso*Quinoline.

BY RAJENDRA NATH SEN AND GOPAL KRISHNA MUKHERJEE.

The present investigation was undertaken with the object of introducing antimony in quinoline and *iso*quinoline nuclei and by the application of Bart's reaction it has been possible to introduce antimony into 3-, 5-, 6-, 7- and 8- positions of the quinoline nucleus. But as during the course of the investigation Morgan and Cook's paper (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 737) dealing with quinoly-5-, 6- and 8- stibinic acids has already appeared only the sodium salts of the corresponding 7- and 5-derivatives are described in this paper.

It has been observed that the position of the amino group in the quinoline nucleus is of very great consequence. Thus 2- and 4-aminoquinolines do not even respond to the diazo reaction (Mills and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 741; Claus and Frobenius *J. pr. Chem.*, 1897, *ii*, 56, 191; Wenzel, *Monatsh.*, 1894, 15, 458), the 6 and 8-aminoquinolines yield only 10 to 15% of the stibinic acids (sodium salt) while 25-30% of the corresponding stibinic acids are obtained from 3-, 5- and 7-aminoquinolines. In the case of *iso*quinoline, however, the yield of the stibinic acid (sodium salt) is comparatively small, being only 5-8% of the theoretical. All the stibinic acids in the free state are more or less amorphous substances though they give sodium salts, which possess well-defined crystalline shape and contain water of crystallisation. It is also interesting to note that the crystalline sodium salts containing water of crystallisation are more or less coloured. The colour of the salts practically disappears on heating due to loss of water of crystallisation but none of them melts or decomposes even at 300°.

It has also been possible to obtain quinoline derivatives with a mercury atom in the nucleus by the action of mercuric acetate on 8-oxyquinoline, the mercury atom entering the quinoline nucleus into the *ortho* or the *para* position to the hydroxyl group, probably in the latter as in the case of α -naphthol which usually gives the *para* compound. Hydroxymercuro-8-oxyquinoline sulphonic and carboxylic acids and a number of allied compounds have also been prepared by Heyden (D. R. P. 283246). Dede and Hessler (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 188, 325) have also described compounds of the type $(C_9H_6ON)HgCl_3$ (C_9H_7ON) prepared from 8-oxyquinoline and mercuric salts.

5-Bromo-8-oxyquinoline and 5:6-dibromo-8-oxyquinoline have been mercurated and it has been found that they also undergo mercuration as easily as 8-oxyquinoline, the mercury atom evidently entering into the *ortho* position to the hydroxyl group. The bromo-oxyquinolines were prepared by brominating 8-oxyquinoline (Claus and Howitz, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1891, *ii*, 44, 433).

That in these compounds the mercury atom is not attached to the oxygen atom is proved by the stability of these compounds towards caustic alkalis, the *o*-mercury compounds being decomposed in the presence of caustic alkali (*cf.* Neogi and Chatterji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, *5*, 221). These compounds are soluble in caustic alkalis instead of being decomposed by them.

These acetoxymercuri derivatives are amorphous powder, insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. On heating they decompose with the liberation of mercury.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Sodium quinolyl-7-stibinate.—7-Aminoquinoline (5 g.) was dissolved in 100 c. c. of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) and diazotised. Antimony trichloride solution prepared by dissolving antimony trioxide (5 g.) in concentrated hydrochloric acid (19 c. c.) was added slowly with stirring to the diazo solution containing a further quantity of concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.). On keeping for an hour in ice the crystalline precipitate was filtered at the pump, washed with hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.2) and then with water till free from acid. The mass was then beaten up with distilled water and caustic soda solution (6 g. in 20 c.c.) was added gradually to it with vigorous mechanical stirring when evolution of nitrogen took place. The whole was then allowed to stand overnight after which the solution was filtered and the residue extracted with a small quantity of boiling water. The combined filtrates were acidified with acetic acid and allowed to settle. The gelatinous precipitate was washed several times with water by decantation after which it was emulsified with water, warmed on the water-bath and a few drops of caustic soda solution were added when the precipitate dissolved. On concentrating the solution on the water-bath the sodium salt began to separate. It was collected, washed with alcohol and obtained as an almost colourless substance not melting up to 300°. (Found: N, 4.32; Sb, 34.82. $C_9H_7O_3NNaSb, H_2O$ requires N, 4.14; Sb, 35.5 per cent).

Sodium quinolyl-3-stibinate was obtained from 3-aminoquinoline, prepared according to Mills and Watson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 741); silky needles slightly orange in colour and not melting up to 300°. (Found: N, 3.92; Sb, 36.10. $C_9H_7O_3N NaSb, H_2O$ requires N, 4.14; Sb, 35.5 per cent).

Sodium isoquinolyl-5-stibinate was prepared from 5-aminoisoquinoline in the same way as above in light greyish brown needles not melting up to 300°. (Found: N, 3.85; Sb, 35.18. $C_9H_7O_3N Na Sb, H_2O$ requires N, 4.14; Sb, 35.5 per cent).

5-Acetoxymercuri-8-oxyquinoline.—An aqueous solution of mercuric acetate (15 g.) acidulated with acetic acid (5 c.c.) was added rapidly with stirring to a solution of 8-oxyquinoline (5 g.) in caustic soda solution (2.5 g. in 250 c. c. of water) when a voluminous precipitate separated. The solution, acid to litmus, was then allowed to stand for an hour after which the supernatant clear liquid was siphoned off. The precipitate was then washed several times with water by decantation, filtered at the pump, washed with water, dried and then washed several times with hot benzene to remove any excess of 8-oxyquinoline. It is a beautiful red powder, decomposing above 280°, insoluble in glacial acetic acid and in alcohol. It is soluble in caustic soda and also in moderately strong hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 3.05; Hg, 49.1. $C_{11}H_9O_3NHg$ requires N, 3.47; Hg, 49.63 per cent).

7-Acetoxymercuri-5:6-dibromo-8-oxyquinoline was prepared from 5:6-dibromo-8-oxyquinoline as above, the dried product being finally treated several times with hot alcohol to remove dibromo-oxyquinoline. It is a yellow powder decomposing at 180-81°, insoluble in glacial acetic acid and in common organic solvents, soluble in caustic alkalis which do not decompose it. It is, however, soluble in moderately strong hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 2.95; Hg, 34.93. $C_{11}H_7O_3NBr_2Hg$ requires N, 2.5; Hg, 35.65 per cent).

7-Acetoxymercuri-5-bromo-8-oxyquinoline was prepared from 5-bromo-8-oxyquinoline. It is a yellow powder decomposing at 231-32°, insoluble in glacial acetic acid and in common organic solvents but soluble in caustic alkali. (Found: N, 3.06; Hg, 40.64. $C_{11}H_8O_3NBr Hg$ requires N, 2.9; Hg, 41.5 per cent).

